

COMMON COMPETENCES FOR THE PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE DRAWING TEACHERS

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ANNOTATION. Teacher's professional competence means a set of professional and personal qualities necessary for the successful implementation of teaching activities. This article examines the professional development competence of the future drawing teacher.

Key words: professional competence, modern education, professional development, future teacher, skills and competence, teacher activity.

INTRODUCTION

The changes taking place in the modern education system ensure the need to increase the teacher's qualifications and professional skills, that is, his professional competence. The main goal of modern education is to meet the current and future needs of the individual, society and the state, to train a person who is fully competent as a citizen of his country, capable of social adjustment in society, able to start work, and self-educate. education and self-improvement. A free-thinking teacher who predicts the results of his activity and models the educational process is a guarantee of achieving his goal. It is for this reason that in the modern, rapidly changing world, there is a sharp increase in the demand for a qualified, creatively thinking, competitive teacher who is able to educate a person.

MAIN PART

Based on modern requirements, we can identify the main ways to develop a teacher's professional competence:

- Work in stylistic associations, creative groups;
- Research activity;
- Innovative activity, development of new pedagogical technologies;
- Different forms of pedagogical support;
- Active participation in pedagogical contests and festivals;
- Broadcast your educational experience;
- Use of ICT, etc.

But none of the listed methods will be effective if the teacher himself does not realize the need to improve his professional skills. This means the need to create motivation and favorable conditions for pedagogical growth. It is necessary to create conditions in which the teacher independently realizes the need to improve the level of his professional qualities. Analyzing one's pedagogical experience activates the teacher's professional self-development, as a result of which research skills are formed, which are then combined with teaching activities. The teacher should participate in the process of managing the school's development, which will help to improve his professional skills.

Development of professional competence is a dynamic process of assimilation and modernization of professional experience, which leads to the development of personal

professional qualities, accumulation of professional experience, implies continuous development and self-improvement.

One of the important conditions of personnel training in art and pedagogic higher educational institutions consists of two main aspects: on the one hand, training of highly qualified teachers, and on the other hand, training of professional artists in a broad sense. The drawing teacher at the school should have professional competences that allow children to develop aesthetic taste, artistic perception, imagination, fantasy, activate creative activity, and develop practical and drawing skills. All this sets new serious tasks for higher education in terms of comprehensive improvement of training of future drawing teachers, formation of professional competencies, artistic and pedagogical qualities of the teacher. In this regard, it is necessary to pay the most serious attention to the methods of formation and development of students' professional skills at the university.

For a drawing teacher, artistic, creative and pedagogical skills come first, the level of their development is directly proportional to the quality of professional activity. Therefore, effective and rational development of pedagogical and artistic-creative skills among students of art and pedagogic higher education institutions is one of the most important problems of education. Classes on the methodology of teaching drawing are aimed at forming professional competence and artistic-pedagogical qualities in students. Special attention should be paid to the basic principles of creating a realistic image of objects. "Our main goal is to bring the child's visual activity closer to the elementary foundations of a full-fledged real image through rational guidance and systematic training." Therefore, students should have sufficient experience in pedagogical drawing of the objects provided for in the higher education program.

Improving the efficiency of professional and artistic training of future drawing teachers is related to the active use of sketches and sketches that develop artistic perception of reality and contribute to the formation of an artistic image in the teaching of academic drawing. expressive means of visual art language. "The role of the sketch in the pedagogical activity of the drawing teacher is extremely important. The teacher constantly makes various drawings in front of all students, shows his explanations with them, shows drawing on a work or subject taken from life, etc.

Analysis of the teaching of drawing in different classes, the stock of educational equipment in the classrooms and its use, interviews with teachers revealed that teachers do not always clearly understand the role of pedagogical drawings on the blackboard in the process of teaching visual arts. . Often, teachers try to replace the pedagogical pictures on the blackboard with standard visual aids, the external actions of the teacher do not correspond to the internal actions of students, and the model of knowledge and skills being formed is not appropriate.

Students of higher educational institutions for the first time face the problem of making pedagogical drawings on the blackboard during their teaching practice and often get lost in front of it. The reason for students' lack of confidence is not a lack of good preparation for academic drawing, it is a combination of many factors.

First, the student has not yet developed a sense of format. If until now he had to work on a sheet of Whatman paper or a canvas of the same size, then a board with an area several times larger than Whatman paper appears in front of him. Drawing on paper is done at arm's length, and the drawing is designed to be perceived from 2-3 meters; the image on the board

should be suitable for the size of the classroom and designed for normal perception of the image by students sitting at the back desks.

Secondly, the beginning teacher mechanically transfers the entire method of transferring the pedagogical drawing from paper to the blackboard, which is not always justified. , academic drawing with stages of generalization. requires a long time, drawing on the board requires speed of execution, clarity, compactness, ease of perception.

Thirdly, the perception of white lines against the background of a dark board without matching is another important problem in drawing with chalk on the board. For example, in botany, geography or physics classes, white line images on the blackboard do not distract either the teacher or the students, but it is different in visual arts classes. Without special psychological training, it is very difficult to perceive a white shadow in the depicted object, where there should be a shadow and vice versa (negative image).

It should be noted that each drawing on the board is actually a sketch, because it is usually done immediately, without interruption, and very quickly. This speed is determined by the conditions of the lesson, when it is necessary to allocate as much time as possible for independent work of schoolchildren from 45 minutes. Therefore, you can spend a maximum of 3-4 minutes for each drawing done on the board.

CONCLUSION

In short, drawing science programs have deepened their knowledge of specialized disciplines and mastered the technological competencies outlined in the Bachelor of Science in Drawing Qualifications. The development of design competence requires the formation of graphic knowledge, skills, skills and abilities, taking into account the requirements set out in public education standards, employers' proposals, trends in the development of science, technology and technology.

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